

Asia Pacific Biospecimens Open Forum - Virtual Event
March 3rd 2023
Discussing the International Use of Biospecimen and Associated Data

Hosts: Dr. Kazuhiko Yamamoto, Dr. Annette Schmid and Mayumi Kusunose

Welcome Remarks

Speakers: Kazuhiko Yamamoto

This is the second forum hosted by the Science Policy Think Tank. The first forum focused on European and American research, but today's open forum was intended to continue the conversation from the Asia-Pacific perspective. This forum was also intended to enable discussion of the challenges faced by sharing and using human biological samples and associated data.

The Riken Center for Integrative Medical Sciences conducts a diverse range of scientific research in order to translate findings into clinical solutions for humanity. International collaboration allows the center to advance scientific research and improve health for all. As data protection regulations become more complex around the world, international scientific collaboration becomes more difficult and research slows down. At the same time, however, scientists recognize the importance of privacy and data protection of research subjects and the need to collaborate with research subjects and the public.

Hopefully, today's sessions with many distinguished researchers and advocates will enable us to overcome the challenges facing biomedical research.

Introduction and Background

Speakers: Mark Barnes, Marianna Bledsoe

Moderators: Mayumi Kusunose, Dr. Annette Schmid

The first panel discussion included a review of previous and planned programs and initiatives related to international use of biospecimens and associated data.

The Science Policy Thinktank was founded in October 2020 as an independent group of policy experts from across industry, academia, non-profit organizations and independent consultants.

The Thinktank facilitated a first, virtual and public forum on strengthening global research with Biospecimens and associated data in an ethical and socially responsible way in December 2021.

From that first open forum that focused on the US, Europe and Africa, it was learned that there is great interest and need to work with patients and the public on preferences, value, and risks of biospecimens use and an opportunity to collaborate internationally towards a more harmonized legal framework for biospecimen and data sharing.

The International Society for Biological and Environmental Repositories (ISBER) hosts events and facilitates collaboration regarding biobanking issues, including those related to international biospecimen and data sharing. The International Society for Biological and Environmental Repositories (ISBER) is a global biobanking organization that provides a forum for addressing emerging challenges to repository

operations (For more information see www.isber.org). At an ISBER Virtual Roundtable held on June 14, 2022, participants discussed international biospecimen and data sharing challenges and identified the need to develop guiding principles or a code of ethics for the international sharing of and secondary research with biospecimens and associated data. From a bioethics perspective, the issue of secondary use is a crucial one. Building international standards will help advance bioethics and ultimately advance research and the human race.

As a follow on to this meeting, an ISBER Workshop will be held May 3, 2023 from 3:30 – 5:30 pm at the ISBER Annual Meeting in Seattle: Building Bridges: Towards An International Framework for Specimen Sharing (For more information see <https://www.isber.org/page/ISBER2023AnnualMeeting>).

The International Society for Biological and Environmental Repositories (ISBER) hosts events and facilitates collaboration regarding biobanking issues. One of ISBER's goals is to create an international ethical framework to facilitate global specimen and data sharing that facilitates research and respects participant's privacy rights.

The Multi-Regional Clinical Trials Center (MRCT) at Harvard University and Brigham and Women's also operates in this space. MRCT recognizes that at the international level there is a patchwork of regulations about the use, storage, transportation, retention, disposition, secondary use of biospecimens. Additionally, there are additional restraints on the phenotypic and demographic information attached to the biospecimens. As a result, scientists around the world face regulatory obstacles to using biospecimens.

Today's event looks at two major considerations for the international use of biospecimens and associated data: (1) the legislation, funding and regulations that apply to biospecimens and their associated data across countries and (2) the appropriate ethical standards for the use of biospecimens and associated data must be accounted for when establishing and operating a biobank (e.g., participant consent, including oversight, and proper limitations on future use of biospecimens).

Session 1: Hurdles and Solutions to the Use of Biospecimen and Associated Data

Speakers: Dr. Subasri Armon, Dr. Diah Iskandriati, Dr. Raymond Lin, Dr. Koichi Matsuda, Katherine Wang, Dr. Ngô Anh Tiến

Moderator: Dr. Zisis Kozlakidis

This session facilitated a review of biobanking activities and legislative, regulatory and funding environments in Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore, Japan, Vietnam, and China.

Malaysia

Biobanking in Malaysia began around 2003 and there are currently at least five well-known biobanks that focus on collecting cancer tissues for research purposes. One of the most well-known is the Malaysian Cohort Project by the Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia Medical Molecular Biology Institute (UMBI) Biobank that is a population-based biobank initiated by the prime minister in 2004, passed by the cabinet in 2005 and established in 2006. Currently, the biobank is in Phase 2 where they have completed the specimen collection and are now conducting follow up assessments. The research is focused on

prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of non-communicable diseases. Another notable biobank is the Ministry of Health biobank located in the Institute for Medical Research, National Institutes of Health, Malaysia. This biobank was established in 2009 and focuses on collecting cancer tissues but also works to collect biological specimens. In 2015, the Ministry of Health, Malaysian released a revised guidelines on research involving biological samples but detailed attention to ethical concerns were limited. More should be done to develop ethical guidelines for biobanks in Malaysia. Currently, biobanks still rely on international guidelines to guide their activities. There are limitations on foreign access to Malaysian specimens or associated data, however the present modality is through the approval of the Economic Planning Unit. For example, the Personal Data Protection Act 2010 statute prohibits the transfer of personal data outside Malaysia. As a result, foreign involvement in biobanking only occurs through collaborations between Malaysian and foreign researchers. Broad consents are generally acceptable in Malaysia but there are heightened concerns regarding genetic data.

Indonesia

Indonesia does not have a register of biobanks operating in the country. Biobanking activities are conducted across Indonesia by private organizations, universities, and the government. Current Indonesian regulations target human tissues and cells and other biological specimens – both of which are collected by biobanks operating in the country. Among these activities, Indonesian regulators pay particular attention to in vitro fertilization, stem cell research, and biological specimens. With regard to ethical considerations, Indonesia has established a national Ethics Committee that approves all human tissue research in the country and imposes certain requirements on that research. The Indonesian government is also very strict on international collaboration on research involving human tissue but there are different regulations for human, wildlife, and microorganism samples. Generally, foreign entities must have a collaboration with an Indonesian biobank to use Indonesian samples and biological samples cannot be sent outside the country without an accompanying Indonesian researcher.

Singapore

In Singapore, the Human Biomedical Research Act of 2015 governs human tissue banking. The challenges associated with implementing the law showed the importance of having regulations that can practically be implemented by scientists and the need to have communication between scientists and regulators. Singapore also has substantial reporting requirements for researchers, mandating monthly disclosures of new biobanking activities. The ethical oversight bodies also emphasize training in the biobanking space. For example, in order to proceed on grant-funded research involving biospecimens, scientists must complete specified training on relevant legal requirements and ethical considerations. Training requirements are tailored to the type of research being conducted. Singapore biobanks working with microbiological specimens collaborate frequently with foreign researchers. However, international collaboration in research projects involving human specimens is much more difficult. In Singapore, researchers generally think carefully about the purpose of a biobank and consider privacy, accessibility, and public engagement in the context of the biobank's purpose.

Japan

Japan has three major biobanks. One of which is the Biobank of Japan, which was established twenty years ago to conduct research on human specimens. Clinical tissues are not stored at the Biobank of Japan, only genetic materials and serum samples. Several international companies have inquired about

obtaining Japanese data, but transmittals have not yet occurred. Many biobanks are only available to university researchers, meaning that private sector researchers (e.g., from pharmaceutical companies) cannot access the samples stored in the biobanks across the country. International companies have access to aggregated data but cannot yet obtain specimens and associated data at the individual level. Further, biospecimens and associated human data are not sent outside of Japan due to the regulatory and privacy concerns related with such transmission. Despite these hurdles, international research cooperation is still possible in Japan. Japanese researchers often obtain broad consents from patients at the time of specimen collection which enables researchers to conduct secondary research more easily than in other contexts.

Vietnam

In Vietnam, there is an old biobank of microorganisms held by the national university. Human tissue banks in Vietnam are regulated by national legislation that governs the collection, storage, and distribution of human tissues. A current biobanking project focuses on colon cancer and has collected over 100,000 samples to discover biomarkers for colon cancer and drive clinical outcomes for patients. There are several biobanking projects across Vietnam that focus on a wide range of human diseases. Human tissue research typically involves collaboration between a researcher and a hospital or university. The Ministry of Health permits the transmission of human samples and associated data with Vietnamese and foreign researchers so long as an agreement is in place between the two sharing entities. Consent is obtained from patients at the time of collection and does not present an obstacle to subsequent data sharing in Vietnam. The Ministry of Health has encouraged hospitals to open biobanking operations in order to preserve the biological specimens of the country – encouraging news for biobanking efforts which are still new to Vietnam.

China

In China, there is no single regulation or law that governs the management and operations of biobanks. Ethical and quality management standards have been established by the government, but they are not binding. An important regulation governs the collection, use, preservation, and transfer of Chinese patients' genetic materials and prohibits the preservation of such materials by foreign entities. As a result, biobanks established by Chinese hospitals and research institutions collaborate with foreign entities and facilitate access to data. Foreign entities can collaborate with Chinese organizations but cannot own the biobank or the genetic materials. The Chinese ethical guidelines required researchers to obtain consent if samples are used for secondary research purposes that are outside the scope of the original consent. This requirement creates operational issues for biobanks in China because it can be difficult to track down patients. Foreign entities continue to struggle with the application and reach of Chinese regulations because the government typically does not issue guidance at the time regulations are initially released. The best course of action for researchers and institutions is to closely monitor regulatory developments in China with your counsel and advisors to make sure your business complies with the law in a way that is commercially sensible. Generally, when operating in China, the key is to remain flexible and open minded in the face of ever-changing regulatory regimes.

Session 2: Diversity within and Representativeness of Biospecimens for Secondary Research

Speakers: Yasuyoshi Arimatsu, Dr. Allamanda Faatoese, Paula Kim, Dr. Partha Majumder, Dr. Jay Shin

Moderator: Helen Morrin

The third panel discussion included a review of the importance of diversity and representativeness in biospecimens and the importance of community engagement in the establishment and operation of biobanks. The below paragraphs reflect the flow of the conversation of the panelists and moderator.

Biobanking in the Asia Pacific region and elsewhere requires an approach that takes into account diverse community beliefs and preferences. Among communities around the world, there is great interest in biobanking research and the potential to develop personalized medicines that benefit all. It is important for researchers and governments to collaborate with community members at the onset of biobanking activities in a transparent fashion. Communities generally want to contribute to research and improved clinical outcomes, but they also want to feel involved and engaged in the process and protected. Communities also want to know that the research is conducted for the purpose of improving clinical health outcomes that affect them. Community engagement should be considered in terms of the development of long-term relationships and include communicating activities conducted at the biobank and the results of the research. When communicating research objectives to communities, biobanks should be careful to avoid stereotyping communities and furthering the stigmatization of a particular group.

As an example, India is home to a vast array of ethnic communities with different languages, cultures, and economic development levels. Therefore, perceptions of science are highly variable across the Indian population. For example, some communities view blood as a physical continuation of their ancestors – this belief requires blood sample collection to be conducted in a respectful and sensitive manner by researchers. In general, when scientists go to communities to collect samples, reactions differ greatly, particularly with regard to individuality and privacy concerns. Many communities prefer to make communal decisions regarding whether to participate in biospecimen efforts. Effective collection efforts require consistent community engagement and explaining to community members the benefits of participation, answering questions, and gaining community trust. Many Indian communities do not react positively to unfamiliar scientists requesting blood samples and are skeptical of the value research can provide to their communities. This skepticism derives from a history of harmful research studies and communities are aware of the harm such studies could inflict on them and inconsistency with their own cultural values. However, if researchers are prepared to develop a trustworthy relationship it is possible to successfully collect samples from a large population and from a wide range of Indian population groups.

It is important to prepare for the event of a leak of biological data. It is also crucial to take steps to protect participant privacy and prevent discrimination in the development and operation of a biobank. These preparatory steps are critical to earn the trust of the community and increase participation in specimen collections. If there is a leak of biological information, there is risk that the data will be misused, potentially to engage in genetic discrimination. Genetic discrimination is a major concern with the rise of biobanking around the world and researchers and governments should take steps to prevent such discrimination. However, it is also important to remember that there are benefits in integrating genetic information, including furthering ongoing research, that should be balanced against the risks. Biobanks

should take steps to communicate the risk-benefit analysis to donors and communities in order to increase engagement.

Strong governance mechanisms within a biobank can help build community trust and empower scientists to conduct research. Good governance should include mechanisms to inform communities on secondary uses of specimens and fight against misconceptions regarding research. Governance should also include appropriate representation of affected communities, particularly those that are historically underrepresented. Partnerships with communities ensure the appropriate use of samples for research and that donors' perspectives are incorporated into the decision-making process at the biobank. Transparency is another key element to successful biobanking. Transparency includes informing communities of the biobank's purpose, objectives, and operations. Further scientists and biobanks should remember that communities want to know that research is addressing the health concerns affecting them and will eventually lead to new therapeutic developments and improved clinical outcomes. Communities need to trust both the biobank, as an institution, and the research conducted at the biobank. There is an opportunity for collaboration between patient organizations and biobanks to inform governmental authorities on the contours of biomedical research for the purpose of developing regulations that appropriately balance research and ethical concerns.

Biobanks should work with non-governmental organizations as a bridge to build a relationship with the community. Biobanks will develop a legacy in the community that goes beyond the individuals in the biobank – building a sustained relationship over time will help develop positive community relationships. The majority of non-governmental organizations in the Asia-Pacific region are volunteer-driven and have limited staff. This dynamic creates the opportunity for industry and biobanks to collaborate with non-governmental organizations to combine resources and relationships to further biobanking efforts in a manner that is ethical and sustainable for long-term engagements and re-engagements with particular communities. One model is a consortium that trains scientists and other stakeholders including students in countries where biobanking is new. Such a consortium enables collaboration to share best practices among scientists and generate and communicate research findings to a broad range of stakeholders which includes communities and the public.

Data integration is another key to leveraging the power of genetic data and to understand the heterogeneity of the human genome. Such integration is complex when countries establish limits on international data sharing. Genetic researchers should learn from other sectors, including the technology sector, to inform approaches to obtaining patient consent and integrating data across several sources to enhance research capabilities while also taking into account the unique concerns present when collecting and using human genetic data. Data integration in the Asia-Pacific is challenging because of the different approaches taken by governments across the region. The lack of a unified regulatory authority in the biobanking sector, means that data integration involving biospecimens can become a geopolitical issue as governmental authorities try to prevent foreign transmission or use.

Wrap Up

Speaker: Mark Barnes

Most patients want their specimens to be used for constructive medical research rather than being left to languish in storage facilities. But it also very important to have strong biobanking governance that

includes oversight over specimen use. There needs to be patient participation in biobank governance alongside scientists and funders.

The variation in standards across countries and regions creates challenges for the use of biological specimens and data, including the trans-national shipment of such specimens and data. It is important to understand applicable regulatory requirements and find ways to conduct research within the limitations set forth in a given country or region.

There is a widespread use of broad consent for biobanking, but common concerns remain regarding the scope and effectiveness of broad consent and whether re-consent is required for some specific secondary uses, such as genomic sequencing and genetic testing.

Ultimately, there is a need to define shared ethical principles relating to secondary research uses of biospecimens and associated data, and to do so across the “life cycle” of biospecimens – collection, curation, storage, access, secondary research uses, and disposition. National regulatory regimes and requirements can then be mapped onto these principles, with an ultimate goal of identifying how regulations may differ from accepted ethics, and advocating for convergence among national regulations, so that ethical science can be facilitated.